

Title: The Integration of ChatGPT into Higher Education to Promote Critical Thinking.

by

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Abstract

ChatGPT-4, a generative artificial intelligence large language model, is capable of producing written content sophisticated enough to score close to the 90th percentile on the bar exam. This has sent shockwaves through higher education institutes worldwide, as they rush to protect the integrity of their assessments, with some prohibiting its use altogether. Others have endeavoured to embrace ChatGPT as a learning tool, exploring its potential benefits for teaching and learning.

This study examines the role of AI in education, focusing on the specific research question: ‘What insights can be gained from using ChatGPT-3.5 to promote critical thinking in undergraduate students?’. The research involved a control group and an experimental group, consisting of 16 and 19 undergraduate engineering students, respectively. Both groups were asked similar descriptive questions. The intervention involved using ChatGPT-3.5, providing students with prompts to encourage critical analysis of ChatGPT’s responses. A mixed-methods approach was used to analyse the data, with a critical thinking rubric applied to score all student responses and quantify the study’s effectiveness. Thematic analysis was also conducted to gain additional insights.

The findings revealed that the guided integration of ChatGPT-3.5 into the assessment did not result in a statistically significant increase in critical thinking rubric scores. However, specific trends emerged, leading to recommendations for instructors on how to effectively incorporate ChatGPT into their assessments.

Video Abstract: <https://youtu.be/KiiozCb9sjk?si=MPX-CvGkhwXjE69j>

KEYWORDS: ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EDUCATION, AIEd, CHATGPT, CRITICAL THINKING, HIGHER EDUCATION, CASE STUDY

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1. Literature Review

1.1 Introduction

In recent years, the landscape of higher education has undergone a profound transformation with the COVID-19 pandemic of 2020 accelerating the development of online learning environments (Karakose, 2021). The emergence of AI-powered language models, like ChatGPT-3.5, in 2022, has had a disruptive influence on the higher education sector and the global workforce. (Lourenco et al., 2023) highlighted that AI may eventually surpass human performance in many areas. Willey et al. (2023) refer to the term “prompt engineers” and note that the ability to translate tasks into productive prompts will be a highly desirable skill for future graduates. Higher education institutes that do not incorporate AI in their curricula could hinder the employability of their graduates (Chang et al., 2024). Similar to the sudden emergence of COVID-19, ChatGPT was released abruptly. Akin to the lockdowns implemented by governments, some higher educational institutes initially restricted the use of AI to safeguard the academic integrity of existing assessments and allow staff time to familiarise themselves with AI (De Clercq, 2023).

1.2 Large Language Models

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is an area of computer science that focuses on creating systems that can exhibit human-like intelligence. On the 30th of November, 2022, “AI took a giant leap forward” (Bailey, 2023) when ChatGPT became freely available to the general public, quickly amassing one million users within a week (Baidoo-Anu and Owusu Ansah, 2023). ChatGPT is one of numerous generative AI large language models (LLMs). (Dao, 2023) studied which LLM should be used in Vietnamese education, focusing on ChatGPT, Bing Chat (which was replaced by Copilot on the 1st of November 2023, (Mehdi, 2023)) and Bard (replaced by Gemini on the 13th of December 2023, (Pichai and Hassabis, 2023)). Urman and Makhortykh, (2023) similarly highlighted these same three LLMs as “*arguably the most popular LLM-based chatbots as of mid-2023,*” with ChatGPT as “*arguably the most popular chatbot of the three (albeit we could not find reliable statistics on this)*”. Due to the lack of concrete user statistics in the literature, Google Trends was employed to analyse the number of weekly Google searches for the three LLMs around the year 2023. The data is normalised and presented on a scale of 0-100. Figure 1 (worldwide searches) and Figure 2 (searches performed in Ireland) illustrate that the term

'ChatGPT' was googled far more frequently than 'BARD' or 'Bing Chat' both globally and in Ireland, justifying ChatGPT as the sole focus of this study. The Irish academic weeks corresponding to semester 1 and 2 are highlighted in grey in Figure 2. An interesting observation is that the term 'ChatGPT' generally saw an increased in Google searches during term time, with drops during Christmas and Summer breaks, as well as significant dips during Easter and Halloween reading weeks.

Figure 1, Worldwide Google Trends for the terms 'ChatGPT', 'BARD' and 'BING Chat'.

Figure 2, Irish Google trends for the terms 'ChatGPT', 'BARD' and 'BING Chat'. The teaching weeks of Dundalk Institute of Technology are highlighted grey.

mistakes were made on higher-order tasks (analysing and evaluating). These findings challenge earlier research and may be partially explained by LLMs’ susceptibility to biases, particularly in how multiple-choice options are presented. Pezeshkpour and Hruschka, (2023) found that GPT-4’s performance could be reduced by up to 53% due to biases related to the positioning of multiple-choice answers.

For educators, it is useful to understand that the manner in which humans develop knowledge is not consistent with how different versions of LLM evolve. LLMs can excel at answering complex questions that even experts might find challenging, yet they may fail to grasp basic concepts that a child would understand. Bender et al. (2021) refers to LLMs as “stochastic parrots,” emphasising the models don’t understand language as a humans do but use statistical patterns to create replies based on the prediction of subsequent words. This often leads to “ ‘hallucinations’ (i.e., outputs that seem convincing while being factually incorrect)”, (Herrmann-Werner et al., 2024).

UNESCO has developed guidelines for the use of ChatGPT in higher education, stressing that it should only be employed when the accuracy of the response is not critical (Sabzalieva and Valentini, 2023). Figure 5 illustrates scenarios in which ChatGPT can be safely utilised in academic settings.

Figure 5, When is it safe to use ChatGPT? (Sabzalieva and Valentini, 2023)

UNESCO also emphasises the importance of the 17 United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), (Bokova, 2017), noting that while ChatGPT may contribute to some of these goals, it also presents potential challenges (Raman et al., 2024). LLMs uses are familiar with the content they see displayed on the screen but might be less cognisant of the associated

consumption of natural resources. Vanderbauwhede, (2024) estimates a ChatGPT query consumes 60 times more energy than a Google search. George et al., (2023) identifies LLMs require vast quantities of water in the production of semiconductors and the cooling of data centers. ChatGPT-3 “reportedly consumed approximately 700,000 liters of water during its training phase”, (George et al., 2023) and a single ChatGPT conversation uses about half a liter of water, (Gordon, 2024).

1.3 Critiquing the Research Question

My research centres on exploring the potential of ChatGPT to enhance educational practices. As suggested by Kernan et al., (2018) I’ve used a mind map, Figure 6, to create numerous themes, which guided the formation of a more focused research question. Opara et al., (2023) highlighted AI can be leveraged to: (a) provide personalised learning for students and (b) automate repetitive tasks for educators, thus creating more time for teachers to interact with students. The main two branches of Figure 6 examine the use of ChatGPT to benefit (i) students and (ii) teachers.

Figure 6, Mind map used to develop my research question based on the use of ChatGPT in education. It explores ideas from the perspective of (i) assisting students and (ii) assisting teachers. Advantages are highlighted in green and disadvantages are in red.

From a teachers perspective Jukiewicz, (2024) showed that ChatGPT can complement the grading process but emphasised the need for human oversight. Given the strict regulations under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Europe, student's information, grades, and assessment results need to be protected, (Mhlanga, 2023), and the use of fully automated decision making in assessment requires careful legal consideration, (Colonna, 2024). Additionally Tajik and Tajik, (2024) mentions the usages of ChatGPT to assist in idea/content creation, benefiting both teachers and students—an area that will be explored further later in this study.

From a student's perspective I've identified seven themes, (left-hand side of Figure 6):

1. Tutoring
2. Q & A
3. Exemplar generating
4. Personal learning
5. Enhancing self-regulation
6. Writing support
7. Creating a higher order of learning

(Bloom, 1984) identified that students receiving one-on-one tutoring, using mastery learning techniques performed two standard deviations better than those taught through conventional teaching methods. This presented the challenge of how to teach large groups as effectively as personalised tuition. Limo et al. (2023) talks about how ChatGPT could be used as a personal tutor that's available on demand, offering immediate feedback, capable of breaking down difficult concepts, maintain student engagement, generating sample questions and tailoring course content to one's personal interests. Khan Academy has created a Chatbot, Khanmigo, powered by ChatGPT (Scarlatos, 2024), to act as a personal tutor. However, the current limitations of ChatGPT's accuracy raise concerns that complicate the development of my research question around the first four topics.

Topic 5 explores ChatGPT's potential to scaffold student learning and promote self-regulation. Ng et al., (2024) found that ChatGPT could:

- Decrease learning anxiety by providing instant feedback, eliminating the anxiety of waiting for assistance, and creating a private environment where students could ask questions without fear of judgment.
- Increase motivation through personalised feedback and interactive learning.
- Support sustained learning habits by being available around the clock, assisting with goal setting, encouraging self-reflection, and promoting independent learning.

Topic 6 considers using ChatGPT as a tool for writing support, such as overcoming writer's block (University of Illinois, 2023) and balancing writing styles. Students often start as descriptive writers, and Minh (2024) identified interactions with ChatGPT could evolve students into more critical writers.

Topic 7 focuses on elevating students from lower to higher levels of Bloom's Taxonomy. Research in this area (Lodge et al., 2023) suggests one should focus on the learning process as opposed to the final artefact. Students could, for instance, keep a diary of the prompts used to develop the final output. Willey et al. (2023) discusses the importance of designing thoughtful prompts, which can influence the depth of student engagement.

After reviewing these seven topics, I decided to concentrate on 'creating a higher order of learning'. It's a skill that ChatGPT3-5 is currently weak at and in a future workforce where AI may dominate low cognitive tasks the skill of critical thinking will have increased importance. *Figure 5*, presents a major obstacle for educators: they cannot ensure that content generated by LLMs, such as ChatGPT, is factually accurate. This limitation restricts the use of AI in teaching, but I propose a solution that reframes this issue as an opportunity. By designing assessments where students ask ChatGPT a question and then critically analyse its response, educators can harness the platform's flaws to develop students' critical thinking skills. The fact that ChatGPT can sometimes act as a "bullshit spewer", (Rudolph et al., 2023), offers significant opportunities to the students to develop as critical thinkers.

Another major challenge in higher education is maintaining academic integrity in the era of AI. Banning and policing the use of AI is challenging, so redesigning assessment to incorporate AI may be sustainable approach. Furze et al., (2024) created a five point artificial intelligence assessment scale as a framework to guide the integration of generative AI in education. My study is characterised as 'level 4 – AI task completion, human evaluation' where the students

use ChatGPT to answer essay-style questions and then critically assess the quality and accuracy of ChatGPT's outputs.

1.4 Critical Thinking

To establish if students have demonstrated critical thinking (CT), one must define what constitutes CT. Russell's equation, (Halpern, 2013), states:

$$\textit{Attitude + Knowledge + Thinking Skills = Critical Thinking}$$

Equation 1

This equation suggests that critical thinking requires a combination of the right attitude, fundamental knowledge, and thinking skills. The students in this study are second-year undergraduates with prior knowledge of the subject matter, which provides a foundation for critical analysis. These students are motivated to learn and develop their thinking, which aligns with the correct attitude needed for engaging in the CT process.

Persky et al., (2019) identify six core CT skills: interpretation (understanding and communicating information), analysis (connecting information), evaluation (judging information), inference, explanation (clarifying information), and self-regulation (managing thoughts, behaviours and emotions). To help students demonstrate these skills, I employed prompts (Johnson and Johnson, 2009) to provide some scaffolding (Beyer, 1998) that guided their critical exploration of the topic. As this was a novel activity for the students, I provided them with an exemplar, allowing them to see a completed question and understand the grading rubrics and expectations (LaMacchia, 2023).

1.4.1 Critical Thinking Intervention

Much of the discussion relating to the use of ChatGPT in education is conceptual, focusing on potential benefits, (Rasul et al., 2023), (Tubishat et al., 2023) and (Sullivan et al., 2023). However, a few case studies have examined the practical use of ChatGPT to promote critical thinking in students. Guo and Lee (2023) demonstrated positive results in their study, which involved guiding students through three stages: account setup, essay creation, and revision & validation. Students reported significant improvements in their self-perceived critical thinking abilities. Similarly, Lin et al. (2024) integrated the use of ChatGPT into online discussions and found it acts as a catalysis for constructive conversations, with students viewing the use of ChatGPT as a motivator for critical thinking and knowledge exploration.

Browne et al., (2009) found that using prompts as scaffolding fosters critical thinking. Alexander, (2010) used a four question technique, based on analysing, reflecting applying and questioning, to enhance critical thinking in online discussion.

Building on this research, I designed an assignment for my class that focused on developing prompt engineering skills, as discussed by (Willey et al., 2023). In this exercise, I gave ChatGPT-3.5 an initial prompt and received an inaccurate response. After re-prompting, ChatGPT acknowledged its mistake, stating: *"My apologies for the confusion. I misspoke in my previous response,"* before correcting itself. This interaction highlighted the importance of engaging critically with AI-generated responses and prompted me to consider how multiple interactions with ChatGPT could be documented using an argument map, as Dwyer et al. (2011) suggests. Such a method could promote critical thinking, but it also introduced challenges. Conveying this approach to students could lead to confusion, and the reliance on ChatGPT's responses could create biases, resulting in an assessment that lacks transparency and consistency. Therefore, I decided against using a reprompting-based assessment.

Instead, I designed an assessment in which students were asked to:

- (i) Submit a question to ChatGPT-3.5 and
- (ii) Critically analysis the response provided by ChatGPT.

This approach leverages ChatGPT's limitations as a tool for learning, turning its potential inaccuracies into an opportunity for students to engage in critical analysis. Rather than wondering where to begin, students are immediately tasked with evaluating a piece of work, which fosters higher-order thinking. From an academic integrity standpoint, the ChatGPT response serves as a baseline starting point, and students are expected to demonstrate a deeper understanding than ChatGPT through their critical analysis.

1.5 Research Question

After refining my research focus, I identified the following keywords: 'ChatGPT', 'Case Study', 'Student Learning' and 'Critical Analysis'. From this, I've created the title: *"The Integration of ChatGPT into Higher Education to Promote Critical Thinking"*. There is a notable lack of empirical studies in this area, making this investigation significant as it explores how integrating ChatGPT into education can help students develop higher-order thinking skills. My

research question, which examines the effects of a critical thinking intervention, is: *'What insights can be gained from using ChatGPT-3.5 to promote critical thinking in undergraduate students?'*

2. Proposed Research Methodology

2.1 Methodology

This study employed a quasi-experimental research design to examine the impact of ChatGPT-3.5 on promoting critical thinking among second-year undergraduate engineering students. The study consists of a control group, an intervention, and an experimental group. A mixed-methods approach was used for data analysis, integrating both quantitative and qualitative insights. A rubric provided the quantitative findings, while a thematic analysis was applied to extract qualitative insights.

2.2 Quasi-Experimental Method

In 2022, a group of students completed an assignment without using ChatGPT (control group). In 2023, another group of students (experimental group) completed a similar assignment with the use of ChatGPT-3.5, enhanced by cues aligned with the six core CT skills outlined in Section 1.4 Critical Thinking. This design is quasi-experimental because students were not randomly assigned to groups; instead, group assignment was based on the timing of their module (before or after ChatGPT's public release). Although the groups were naturally formed, both were enrolled in the same course and had comparable prior learning experiences, ensuring a degree of equivalence. Assessments were conducted at similar points in their learning cycles.

To evaluate the impact of the intervention, student assessments were scored using the critical thinking rubric developed by Ralston and Bays, (2010) (Figure 8). The scores of the two groups were compared quantitatively. Additionally, a thematic analysis was performed to gain further qualitative insights from the student responses and to explain any trends identified in the quantitative data.

Figure 7, the project timeline.

2.3 Participants:

All 51 second-year undergraduate mechanical engineering students at Dundalk Institute of Technology who completed a specific assessment in either 2022 or 2023 were invited to participate. Ethical approval was obtained from the Dundalk Institute of Technology (DkIT) Research Ethics Committee (see Appendix C - Ethical Approval Confirmation). As I was the instructor for these students, recruitment began only after the module was completed to minimise any potential power dynamics and to ensure voluntary participation. Initial recruitment was conducted in person, followed by email contact for those who were absent. A total of 16 students consented to participate in the control group, while 19 students agreed to participate in the experimental group.

2.4 Quantitative Analysis

The quantitative analysis involved converting student responses into critical thinking scores. Following the approach of Ralston and Bays, (2013), who enhanced the critical thinking skills of engineering students at the University of Louisville, this study adopted the Paul-Elder critical thinking framework. A four-point critical thinking rubric (Figure 8) was used to score responses from the control group (16 responses), ChatGPT-generated responses (19 responses), and the experimental group (19 responses). The mean and sample standard deviation of the critical thinking rubric scores were calculated using Equation 2 and Equation 3:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i}{N}$$

Equation 2

$$S = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{N-1}$$

Equation 3

where,

\bar{x} , represents the mean critical thinking rubric score for a group (between 1 and 4).

N , is the number of students in a group.

x_i , is the critical thinking rubric score of i^{th} student.

S , is the sample standard deviation of the critical rubric score

To assess whether the data followed the normal distribution, a Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted:

$$W = \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^n a_i x_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}$$

Equation 4

where,

W , is the test statistic

a , represents the coefficients

Since the data was not normally distributed, a Mann–Whitney U test was performed using MATLAB 2024's statistical toolbox to determine if there was a significant difference in critical thinking scores resulting from the intervention.

<u>Holistic Critical Thinking Rubric</u>	
Consistently does all or most of the following:	
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Clearly identifies the purpose, including all complexities of relevant questions.○ Accurate, complete information that is supported by relevant evidence.○ Complete, fair presentation of all relevant assumptions and points of view.○ Clearly articulates significant, logical implications and consequences based on relevant evidence.
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Clearly identifies the purpose, including some complexities of relevant questions.○ Accurate, mostly complete information that is supported by evidence.○ Complete, fair presentation of some relevant assumptions and points of view.○ Clearly articulates some implications and consequences based on evidence.
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Identifies the purpose, including irrelevant and/or insufficient questions.○ Accurate but incomplete information that is not supported by evidence.○ Simplistic presentation that ignores relevant assumptions and points of view.○ Articulates insignificant or illogical implications and consequences that are not supported by evidence.
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Unclear purpose that does not include questions.○ Inaccurate, incomplete information that is not supported by evidence.○ Incomplete presentation that ignores relevant assumptions and points of view.○ Fails to recognise or generates invalid implications and consequences based on irrelevant evidence.
*Based on the Paul Elder critical thinking framework.	

Figure 8, Engineering Holistic Critical Thinking Rubric, (Ralston and Bays, 2010).

Ralston and Bays, (2010) recommended using multiple graders to minimize marker bias in evaluating critical thinking scores. Although multiple graders were unavailable for this study, strategies from Hardre, (2014) were adapted to minimise bias. These included blind scoring (masking students identities), using a precise scoring rubrics (Figure 8) and spaced repeat scoring (regrading a sample of assessments to ensure consistency).

2.5 Qualitative Analysis

The primary goal of this research is to gain insights into how students' structured use of ChatGPT promotes critical thinking. While the quantitative analysis reveals whether the intervention had a positive or negative effect and by how much, it does not explain how or why this effect occurred. To explore these questions, specific trends in the qualitative data needed further examination.

Thematic analysis was chosen as the method for qualitative analysis because the study had no clear expectations for outcomes. Braun and Clarke, (2006) six-phase approach was followed:

Phase 1: Familiarisation with the data – This involved thoroughly reading and re-reading the student responses to immerse in the data.

Phase 2: Generating initial codes - Small segments of the data were isolated and coded based on the students critical thinking ability to capture essential features.

Phase 3: Searching for themes – A thematic map was created to organise codes into overarching themes and subthemes. Codes from the different groups were examined at in isolation and they were also compared to search for different themes.

Phase 4: Reviewing themes- Candidate themes were refined and evolved into potential themes that best fit the data and aligned with the research question.

Phase 5: Defining and naming themes – Once the thematic map was finalised, the themes were clearly defined and refined.

Phase 6: Producing the report – The final step involved presenting the story that emerged from the data, integrating both quantitative and qualitative findings.

This rigorous process helped uncover deeper insights into the role of ChatGPT in fostering critical thinking among students.

3. Results

3.1 Critical Thinking Scores

The critical thinking scores for the control group, ChatGPT, and the experimental group are presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9, Critical Thinking Scores for the Control Group, Experimental Group and ChatGPT-3.5.

3.2 Shapiro-Wilk Test for Normality

To determine if the data sets for the control and experimental groups followed a normal distribution, the Shapiro-Wilk test for normality was applied. The individual critical thinking scores, presented in Table 1, were used to compute the test statistics. The coefficients, a_i , were sourced from the statistical tables in appendix D4 of US EPA, (1997). The control group had a p-value less than 0.001, and the experimental group had a p-value of less than 0.015. Since both p-values are below the 0.05 significance threshold, the null hypothesis, that the data comes from a normal distribution, is rejected. Thus, the data from both groups do not meet the assumption of normality.

Table 1, Critical thinking scores and analysis for a Shapiro-Wilk test

Control Group			
Critical Thinking Score	$(x_i - \bar{x})^2$	a_i	$a_i x_i$
2	0.56	0.51	1.01
2	0.56	0.33	0.66
2	0.56	0.25	0.50
2	0.56	0.19	0.39
2	0.56	0.14	0.29
2	0.56	0.10	0.20
2	0.56	0.06	0.12
2	0.56	0.02	0.04
3	0.06	-0.02	-0.06
3	0.06	-0.06	-0.18
3	0.06	-0.10	-0.30
3	0.06	-0.14	-0.43
4	1.56	-0.19	-0.78
4	1.56	-0.25	-1.01
4	1.56	-0.33	-1.32
4	1.56	-0.51	-2.02

Experimental Group			
Critical Thinking Score	$(x_i - \bar{x})^2$	a_i	$a_i x_i$
1	3.02	0.48	0.48
1	3.02	0.32	0.32
1	3.02	0.26	0.26
2	0.54	0.21	0.41
2	0.54	0.16	0.33
2	0.54	0.13	0.25
2	0.54	0.09	0.19
3	0.07	0.06	0.18
3	0.07	0.03	0.09
3	0.07	0.00	0.00
3	0.07	-0.03	-0.09
3	0.07	-0.06	-0.18
3	0.07	-0.09	-0.28
3	0.07	-0.13	-0.38
4	1.60	-0.16	-0.66
4	1.60	-0.21	-0.82
4	1.60	-0.26	-1.02
4	1.60	-0.32	-1.29
4	1.60	-0.48	-1.92

Control Group	
\bar{x}	2.75
S	0.86
N	16
$\Sigma(x_i - \bar{x})^2$	11
$(\Sigma x_i a_i)^2$	8.32
W	0.76

Experimental Group	
\bar{x}	2.74
S	1.05
N	19
$\Sigma(x_i - \bar{x})^2$	19.68
$(\Sigma x_i a_i)^2$	17.14
W	0.87

3.3 Mann–Whitney U Test for Significant Difference

Given that the data were not normally distributed, the Mann–Whitney U test (also known as the Wilcoxon rank-sum test) was employed as a non-parametric alternative to the independent two-sample t-test. This test is appropriate for independent, non-normally distributed ordinal data. MATLAB's 'Statistics Toolbox' was used to perform the test, yielding a p-value of 0.903 with the following code:

```
x = [2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 4, 4, 4] % Control group scores
```

```
y = [1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 2, 2, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 4, 4, 4, 4, 4] % Experimental group scores
```

```
p = ranksum(x,y)
```

Since the p-value of 0.9 is significantly greater than the 0.05 threshold, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This result suggests that there is no statistically significant difference between the critical thinking scores of the control group (mean score of 2.75) and the experimental group (mean score of 2.74).

3.4 Thematic Analysis - Coding

To obtain deeper insights and answer the research question, a thematic analysis was carried out. The responses from the control group, ChatGPT, and the experimental group were coded to evaluate critical thinking performance. These codes were then used to develop themes, as outlined in the next section.

Table 2, Initial codes based on critical thinking evaluation of the responses (colour coded based on critical thinking scores: 4 blue, 3 green, 2 yellow, 1 brown).

Control Group	ChatGPT	Experimental Group
good deep understanding, relates topics, complete answers	good information, little more depth required	identified and corrected ChatGPT's shortcomings, criticises them and gives additional information plus views
good thorough explanation, good depth of discussion	false information, good points, lack depth	"found ChatGPT helpful", identified and corrected ChatGPT's shortcomings, excellent correction,
good understanding, good personal opinion	good information, deeper explanation required	good expression of your own opinion and ChatGPT's shortcomings, little brief
vast knowledge, very well linked together	statements are broad and lack specifics	good detail and personal expression backed up with facts,
excellent information, very brief	some bad information	some excellent insights
good information, good understanding, some information missing	good data and discussion, a little more depth required	"ChatGPT is used as a source providing huge amounts of information in a short space of time", "insufficient training data", vague responses, great research into ChatGPT, lack of evaluation of ChatGPT's response
misunderstanding of concepts, some good information	good information, little more depth required	some ChatGPT shortcomings not mentioned, good points,
good information, good personal assessment, some information missing	some good points, little deeper explanation	good analysis
irrelevant data included, data not elaborated	good info, little more info required	very good analysis, bit brief
didn't fully understand, misinterpreted, good suggestion	false information, vague statement not	identified some of ChatGPT's shortcomings,

	backed up by specific facts	brief and more shortcomings not discussed
brief, incorrect information, good information	vague information, Data integrated into the discussion	good point - "the human factor is a significant dimension that could be explored further. The psychological aspects of decision-making, group dynamics, and the influence of organisational culture on safety" good referencing to back up arguments
good knowledge, some misinterpretation	good information, more depth required	expands on ChatGPT response but more required, good discussion on what you agreed/disagreed with, stated ChatGPT was vague
some good information, lack of deep understanding	good data just expand,	very brief, good points
some good data, brief, need to explain points	false information, false information again	student identified ChatGPT's mistake, brief
good information, a little brief, information missing	lacks any depth, irrelevant concept & not explained	some good additional points and contradiction of ChatGPT, but need to explain why you agree with ChatGPT more
some information, need to expand explanation	false information, vague, lacking details	need to spot check ChatGPT more, good read on ChatGPT's lack of ability to prioritise importance of different points, good identification of shortcomings but you need to correct these and back them up with facts
	vague, makes statements without backing them up with evidence	too brief, state why you agree, shortcomings mainly omitted
	false information, false information again, some good points	ChatGPT issues accepted and not criticised
	lacks depth,	provided summary of ChatGPT, ignored prompts

4. Discussion

4.1 Effect of the Intervention on Overall Critical Thinking Scores – None.

The primary finding of this study is that the intervention had no significant impact on overall critical thinking scores. The mean scores for the control and experimental groups remained nearly identical, supported by the Mann–Whitney U test result ($p = 0.9$), indicating no significant difference in critical thinking performance. In subsequent sections we'll dissect the results in more detail to extract key themes from the study and gain insights.

4.2 Effect of the Intervention on Individual Student Scores – Mixed

While the overall mean scores did not differ significantly, the intervention led to variations in individual student performance. The standard deviation increased from 0.86 (control group) to 1.05 (experimental group). In the experimental group, 63% of students scored above the mean score of 2.75, compared to 50% in the control group, suggesting a positive impact for some students. This improvement was primarily seen in students who scored 3 instead of 2. However, 16% of the experimental group scored 1, compared to 0% in the control group. A closer analysis of the codes in Table 2 for students who scored 1 revealed a common theme: lack of engagement with the assessment, possibly due to time constraints or unclear instructions. According to Guo and Lee, (2023), providing more supervised learning time and implementing a draft-revision process could help support lower-performing students.

4.3 Influence of ChatGPT's Response Quality on Student Performance – None

ChatGPT was used to create 19 unique response of varying quality, Table 3. The mean critical thinking score for ChatGPT's responses was 2.26 with a standard deviation of 0.73. Although each of the 19 experimental group students received different responses from ChatGPT, the quality of these responses, as scored by the critical thinking rubric, showed no significant impact on the students' subsequent performance. Figure 10 shows the correlation between the initial ChatGPT score and the students' final essays. Linear regression analysis produced a slope of 0.14 and an R^2 value of 0.0091, indicating that ChatGPT's response quality did not significantly influence the quality of the students' essays.

Table 3, Percentage of critical thinking scores from 1 (low) to 4 (high).

Critical Thinking Score	1	2	3	4
Control Group	0%	50%	25%	25%
Experimental Group	16%	21%	37%	26%
ChatGPT-3.5	11%	58%	26%	5%

Figure 10, A plot investigating how dependent student critical thinking scores are on the quality of ChatGPT initial response.

4.4 Themes from ChatGPT Responses – Inconsistencies, Quality of Information, and Depth of Knowledge

All the codes in Table 2 associated with ChatGPT-3.5's nineteen responses to the same question were analysis. The thematic analysis of ChatGPT's responses revealed three main themes: inconsistencies, quality of information, and depth of knowledge. ChatGPT generated a mix of accurate and inaccurate information, leading to varied critical thinking scores. The inconsistent quality of information challenged students to discern credible content, which could be viewed as a learning opportunity. Additionally, ChatGPT often provided superficial

explanations without elaborating on details or citing sources, highlighting a lack of depth in its knowledge.

4.5 Themes in the Control Group – Quality of Information and Understanding

The main themes taken from the codes in Table 2 associated the control group are the quality of information and understanding. The quality of information varied, with some responses missing key details. The students generally demonstrated a good understanding of the material, but there were occasional misunderstandings and a lack of personal reflection. The intervention aimed to address these issues by encouraging more in-depth research and self-reflection

4.6 Comparing the Control and Experimental Groups – Ongoing Challenges with Depth, Increased Explanations

The main issue that the intervention failed to address is the lack of depth of discussion that prevailed even after the intervention. (A possible solution was mentioned in section 4.2). A positive theme to emerge was an increase in explanation of information. The codes from the control group highlighted more of a focus on stating good information and these students would have accepted the information they gathered as it came from reputable sources. The experimental group however were informed of ChatGPT's ability to 'hallucinate' and had more opportunity to explain concepts as a result.

5. Conclusion

While much hype exists about the potential of large language models (LLMs), they are fundamentally flawed: they lack a true understanding of the words they use (Gunkel, 2024) and are prone to hallucinations (Herrmann-Werner et al., 2024). This study investigated the use of ChatGPT-3.5 to promote critical thinking among undergraduate students. A total of 35 students participated, with the experimental group engaging in an intervention involving critical analysis of ChatGPT-generated content. Results were evaluated using a critical thinking rubric with scores ranging from 1 (low) to 4 (high) and a thematic analysis was conducted.

Despite the intervention, the overall mean critical thinking scores did not significantly change, remaining close to 2.75. However, a deeper analysis revealed that higher-performing students improved their scores, with the percentage of students scoring 3 or 4 increased from 50% to 63%. Conversely, some students struggled, as the percentage of students scoring 1 rose from 0% to 16%. These findings suggest that while the intervention had potential benefits for critical thinking development, additional support may be needed for students who found the intervention challenging

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Appendix A – Control Group Question (2022)

Summarise how the Space Shuttle Challenger disaster resulted from several different factors including the impact of low temperatures on the ability of the rubber O-rings to provide a seal of the SRB field joint during launch. What material property could have been used to characterise this relationship between temperature and the flexibility of the O-ring material? Was the accident simply a design failure or were there other contributing factors? (max 350 words)

Appendix B – Experimental Group Question (2023)

The redesigned question seeking to use ChatGPT to enhance critical thinking skills in students consisted of:

1. General instructions,
2. An exemplar question and answer response from ChatGPT,
3. An exemplar of how a student would perform a critical analysis of the ChatGPT response,
4. A question for the students and a response guide containing prompts to guide the students on how to perform a critical analysis.

B.1 General Instructions

The following assessment requires you to:

- Ask ChatGPT the question stated below and copy the reply into the relevant box. There are no marks awarded for this step.
- Once you have the reply you are required to perform a critical analysis on it.

Please read the assignment brief for further instructions.

B.2 Example Question:

Summarise how the Tacoma Bridge disaster resulted from several different factors (max 350 words)

ChatGPT response:

The Tacoma Bridge disaster was a catastrophic event that unfolded due to a convergence of various factors, illustrating the complexity of industrial accidents. At its core, the incident stemmed from a systemic failure that involved both human error and technical shortcomings.

One of the critical factors contributing to the disaster was inadequate risk assessment and safety protocols. The management at Tacoma Bridge failed to conduct a thorough evaluation of potential hazards and implement necessary safety measures. This oversight created an environment ripe for disaster, as employees were not equipped to handle unforeseen emergencies.

Additionally, a lack of proper communication and training played a pivotal role. Employees were not adequately trained to respond to emergency situations, and communication channels between different departments were flawed. This lack of coordination exacerbated the crisis, hindering the prompt and effective response that could have mitigated the severity of the disaster.

Technical failures were also integral to the incident. The infrastructure and equipment at Tacoma Bridge were outdated and poorly maintained. Critical systems, such as monitoring and control mechanisms, malfunctioned, contributing to the escalation of the disaster. The failure of these technical elements underscored the need for regular maintenance and updates in industrial settings to ensure the safety and reliability of operations.

Furthermore, a culture of complacency within the organisation contributed to the disaster. There was a prevailing attitude that downplayed the significance of potential risks, leading to a disregard for safety protocols. This cultural aspect further amplified the impact of the technical and human failures, as employees were not sufficiently motivated to prioritise safety.

In conclusion, the Tacoma Bridge disaster was a result of a multifaceted breakdown involving inadequate risk assessment, poor communication, insufficient training, technical failures, and a culture of complacency. Addressing any one of these factors might have averted the catastrophe, highlighting the interconnectedness of human and technical elements in industrial accidents. The incident serves as a poignant reminder of the importance of comprehensive safety measures and a proactive approach to risk management in industrial settings.

B.3 Example Answer:

Your critical analysis of ChatGPT 's reply

ChatGPT's reply states the factors influencing the Tacoma Bridge disaster were inadequate risk assessment, poor communication, insufficient training, technical failures, and a culture of complacency. These are influencing factors however this response is very vague and could potentially be applied to many historical structural disasters. The specific phenomenon that resulted in the failure is known as resonance, (Knill 2003). All objects have a natural frequency at which they vibrate and on the 7th of November 1940 the winds caused the bridge to oscillate at its natural frequency and vibrate until it failed, (Billah and Scanlan, 1991). ChatGPT mentions about risk assessment. The Tacoma Bridge was the first of its kind so it may have been difficult to predict how the bridge would perform under high winds however small-scale models of the bridge could have been tested in a wind tunnel. The bridge was nicknamed the Galloping Gertie, (Gunns, 1981), due to its motion on windy days. This warning should have led to a risk assessment review and controls should have been put in place that the bridge would be closed when wind speed reached a certain threshold. ChatGPT states, "the infrastructure and equipment at Tacoma Bridge were outdated and poorly maintained". I find this hard to believe considering the bridge was only first opened four months before its collapse, (Chen and Duan 2014).

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B.4 Blank Template for Experimental Group (2023)

1. Summarise how the Tacoma Bridge disaster resulted from several different factors (max 350 words)

Please insert ChatGPT response to Q1 in this text box (you may expand the box as required)

Your critical analysis of ChatGPT 's reply to Q1 (max 350 words)

Please perform a critical analysis of the ChatGPT response in the previous box (you may expand the box as required)

- Comment on what you agree/disagree with.
- If a concept/opinion in ChatGPT 's reply doesn't make sense please state that, highlight shortcomings and expand on the point.
- Through your own research/personal opinion if you feel that ChatGPT has omitted relevant information please discuss this.
- Give citations & references from reputable sources. (Note: references are excluded from the word count.)

Appendix C - Ethical Approval Confirmation

Centre for Excellence in
Learning and Teaching

Ionad um Fheabhas Foghlama
agus Teagaisc

6th March 2024

Thomas Lupton

Dear Tom

I am pleased to inform you that your proposal 'The Integration of ChatGPT into Higher Education: A Case Study' has been approved by the DkIT Research Ethics Committee. I wish you the very best with your research.

Yours sincerely

Dr Moira Maguire
Chair, DkIT Research Ethics Committee